

USING INTERACTIVE METHODS IN TEACHING CHINESE LANGUAGE

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Abstract. *The growing demand in Uzbekistan for learning Chinese and the evolution of relations between China and Uzbekistan define the study's relevance.*

The paper focuses on the key elements of teaching Chinese to students who speak Uzbek using cutting edge, modern technologies. The characteristics of teaching Chinese to Uzbek-speaking pupils are examined in the essay, along with informational resources for use in Chinese language instruction. The article addresses the primary issues that Uzbek students have when learning Chinese and suggests creative solutions for these issues.

Keywords: *Internet, communication skills, listening, hieroglyphs, phonetics, Chinese language, innovative technology, educational technologies, and pedagogical innovation.*

ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ ИНТЕРАКТИВНЫХ МЕТОДОВ В ПРЕПОДАВАНИИ
КИТАЙСКОГО ЯЗЫКА

Аннотация. *Растущий спрос в Узбекистане на изучение китайского языка и эволюция отношений между Китаем и Узбекистаном определяют актуальность исследования. В статье основное внимание уделяется ключевым элементам обучения китайскому языку студентов, говорящих на узбекском языке, с использованием передовых современных технологий. В статье рассматриваются особенности обучения китайскому языку узбекоязычных учеников, а также информационные ресурсы для использования в обучении китайскому языку. В статье рассматриваются основные проблемы, с которыми сталкиваются узбекские студенты при изучении китайского языка, и предлагаются творческие решения этих проблем.*

Ключевые слова: *Интернет, коммуникативные навыки, аудирование, иероглифы, фонетика, китайский язык, инновационные технологии, образовательные технологии и педагогические инновации.*

Introduction. China and Uzbekistan have long-standing friendly relations. The two countries have been strengthening economic, political and cultural ties for many years. The relationship between China and Uzbekistan is marked by rapid expansion, and in recent years, the two countries' collaboration has grown. As a result, there has been a sharp increase in interest in

Chinese culture overall and the Chinese language as a vital part of it in recent decades. The number of students and schoolchildren who want to study Chinese as a foreign language is increasing every.

Teaching Chinese to non-native speakers differs greatly from teaching Chinese to native speakers and calls for certain abilities. When teaching Chinese to non-native speakers, it's important to avoid starting from scratch and instead look for parallels and equivalents in the language that reflect the differences between it and their home tongue. It is therefore important for teachers to help pupils develop new language habits rather than teaching them a new language.

Note that there are significant differences between the objectives and approaches of teaching Chinese as a foreign language in China and Uzbekistan. The teacher of a modern school faces the task of finding new ways and means to create the necessary conditions to ensure the development of students' cognitive interest in learning the Chinese language.

One of these ways of development is the introduction of innovative technologies in the classroom. For effective and rapid learning of the Chinese language, the teacher must use advanced pedagogical technologies, interactive, innovative methods, and communicative media.

Methods. In the modern world, the computer is an integral part of our lives, the classrooms of each school are equipped with computers with Internet access and interactive boards, so it is impossible to imagine a modern Chinese language lesson without the use of information technology. Certainly, the use of computer technology in the educational process always arouses interest in the language among schoolchildren. Thus, the use of Internet resources contributes to the expansion of vocabulary, simple study of Chinese grammar, listening comprehension, and literate writing.

One of the best resources for learning and using a foreign language is the Internet. Through the Internet, you will be able to speak with native speakers.

Writing emails can help with written activities. The most crucial issue is the integration of contemporary communication technologies into the educational process and their appropriate, focused application, which encourages students to take an interest in learning a foreign language and improves learning outcomes. This will raise demand and provide opportunities for the usage of cutting-edge instructional technologies.

At the same time, it should be noted that mastering the Chinese language by Uzbek-speaking listeners, especially at the initial stage, is associated with inevitable difficulties. After all, the Chinese language is one of the most ancient languages.

The unit of the Chinese language is a hieroglyph - a graphic image consisting of a certain number of strokes. The national Chinese language is called Putonghua.

A hieroglyph consists of a radical and a grapheme. Mastering the hieroglyphic writing, which includes a non-alphabetic graphic system, a large number of hieroglyphs, the need to memorize the order of strokes, etc., and the phonetic structure of the language with the presence of specific sounds that are unusual for Russian phonetics, the presence of tones in syllables, as well as some other nuances due to the peculiarities of the Chinese language cause great difficulties in learning the Chinese language.

Discussions and Results. This is why we think it is especially important to introduce non-traditional teaching strategies and technological tools that will keep students' attention, let them participate in language learning, and encourage their active, independent study of foreign language content.

Students can independently listen to audio recorded by native speakers or qualified announcers throughout the beginning phonetic course, which is when phonological hearing is created, reading Chinese syllables is taught, and tones are one of the most significant components of learning Chinese. In order to help students control their pronunciation and correct their errors, there are applications and programs that require you to repeat words, phrases, or sentences after the speaker.

These programs can be of great help in helping students with pronunciation right from the start of their Chinese language studies. Moreover, A teacher can host master classes, competitions, and share fresh and helpful information using platforms like *Zoom* and *Skype*. As a result, students are exposed to a wealth of new information outside of the classroom, which piques their interest in learning.

Additionally, you may arrange conversation clubs on a variety of subjects or host online conferences with fluent speakers.

Furthermore, these days, there are programs and smartphone applications focused on many facets of teaching foreign languages. Based on an analysis of scholarly literature, market research on foreign language mobile applications, and a systematization of users' experiences, the applications for learning Chinese can be broadly categorized into the following groups:

- 1) Mobile applications aimed primarily at improving a specific skill (Radicals, Chinese Number, etc.);
- 2) Mobile applications designed to develop language skills, such as vocabulary and grammar (HSK, HSK Online);
- 3) All-purpose mobile apps (Laoshi, Hello Chinese) created for the all-around improvement of communication proficiency in foreign languages. Naturally, this divide is rather conditional, given that the majority of applications are not restricted to honing a particular skill or

kind of speech activity. Specialized mobile apps caught our attention as a way to optimize and enhance the learning process from the perspective of practical application in the process of teaching a foreign language.

The intellectual and educational program “*Laoshi*” has only recently (2021) entered the market, but many Chinese learners have already found this software to be quite helpful.

This application has a large database, which is one of its benefits. It is categorized by topic and includes vocabulary from HSK and well-known Chinese language textbooks. It is very necessary and convenient that the mobile Internet is not used at all when using the application after it has been downloaded and installed.

As a result, the program is available for usage whenever and wherever. These are essentially cards that include new vocabulary along with a variety of writing and speaking challenges. An algorithm for interval repetition of the learned words has been created for effective memorizing of hieroglyphs.

Despite the fact that the application has a huge number of advantages and positive reviews, we should also note one nuance that not everyone immediately understands, i.e. the application interface is somewhat complicated. And it would be nice if the application could be used on computers or laptops. In conclusion, we should stress that the application is necessary at every level of learning and is helpful for picking up new vocabulary, reviewing existing ones, and understanding various grammatical constructions.

Application “*ChineseSkill*”, is a very good application for beginners. This is a curriculum with a set of various exercises, divided by topics and with intermediate tests. The value of this application is the originality of the exercises, which significantly facilitate the memorization of hieroglyphs at the initial stage of learning Chinese. There is speech recognition and evaluation of handwritten input of hieroglyphs, tone animation, and other various technologies. There are also video lessons with an explanation of this or that grammar. To summarize, the application “*Chinese Skill*” will be useful for students at the initial stage of learning Chinese, but for students with basic knowledge, this application will no longer be relevant.

The downside of this application, in our opinion, is that every fourth or fifth exercise has paid content. Which is not very practical. But overall, the app can be recommended to students who are studying Chinese, it will definitely be useful for them.

The *Owl* app, which teaches Chinese characters, is the following app. It's no secret that learning Chinese characters requires a thorough inspection of the characters, which is the first step in the process the fundamental building block for learning (memorizing) a hieroglyph at the stage of learning Chinese. Each key in the “*SoVa*” application has a little collection of exercises that

can be done numerous times, including how to write the key, how to read it, and how to translate it. All of this helps you rapidly and effectively memorize the key, and it's incredibly handy.

There were a few other issues with the program that were noted. It is worthwhile to use this application, and students should be urged to use it precisely when they are starting to learn Chinese, or more accurately, precisely when we are teaching the keys. However, this application could not be required or interesting for us in the future.

Conclusion. At the present stage, there are quite a lot of tools for teaching Chinese. Using these tools will make the process of learning Chinese for students more interesting and effective, but it is also worth remembering that the use of innovative technologies should be built methodically and competently. Thus, we can conclude that at present, interest in innovations has increased, and the need for new knowledge has become more acute; most Chinese teachers, to one degree or another, use various memorization techniques and information technologies that allow them to effectively master new material. At the same time, it is very important to understand that the successful acquisition of new knowledge largely depends on the personal contribution of students. In addition, we can say that the centuries-old method of "textbook and notebook" is already losing its relevance, and today in the modern pedagogical world, innovative technologies must be included in the learning process. In order to keep up with the times, a teacher must constantly monitor the innovations in information technology, not only navigate the Internet space, but also teach students. Our lives are growing more and more reliant on mobile technologies, which are also expanding our options for social engagement and Internet access. The entire educational process may be significantly impacted by these technology.

Learning will progressively leave classrooms and into students' actual and virtual personal spaces, becoming more collaborative while still being more intimate. Finding new ways to employ mobile technology in order to introduce them to learning as an extension of daily life will be taken into consideration for success.

Summing up, focusing on educational and intellectual uses, for which there are several already available products. Before recommending a specific application to a student, the instructor must use it for a predetermined amount of time.

Understanding which situations call for the usage of a certain application and what training level makes it worthwhile to incorporate it into the curriculum is essential.

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